

Action of Yeast Invertase on Different Substrates

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A sample of invertase has been prepared from brewer's yeast which hydrolyses inulin, sucrose, and raffinose to a considerable degree. Behaviour of this invertase has been found towards inulin to be of a specific character.

The work of Adams *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 1369) has proved the presence of some specific enzymes in certain highly purified invertase preparations. These authors studied the behaviour of several yeast invertase preparations towards substrates containing both sucrose and glycosidic linkages. In their experiments enzymatic hydrolysis with five highly purified invertase preparations were tried on twentyeight carbohydrate substrates and at least four distinct types of invertase were detected, which differed in their behaviour towards the substrates, e.g., sucrose, raffinose, stachyose, inulin, melibiose, and β -phenyl-D-mannoside. These authors observed that the fructofuranoside linkages in the carbohydrate substrates, sucrose and raffinose, were hydrolysed by the same type of invertase preparation and that the common enzyme β -D-fructofuranosidase was responsible for this hydrolysis. There is evidence also of the presence of another enzyme, inulase, which is responsible for the hydrolysis of inulin. This is against what may be expected of the original postulation of Weidenhagen who assumed the hydrolysis to be done by the same β -D-fructofuranosidase. Different rates and ratios of hydrolysis by the various invertase preparations and different optimum pH values suggested the presence of more than one distinct enzyme in the invertase preparations. The methods of purification of invertase involved the use of bentonite in most cases. The author demonstrated the superior adsorption capacity of invertase, purified from ethanol in the cold, as compared with bentonite-purified samples. This ethanol-purified sample has been used in the present investigation to study the relative hydrolytic behaviour of the three carbohydrates and results so obtained have been compared with those by Adams *et al.* and others. The object of such a comparison is to find out the special features of the relative hydrolytic behaviour of the substrates due to the same enzyme preparation, which is precipitated by ethanol in a sufficiently pure condition. Such a study is expected to furnish a clue to the chemical nature of this enzyme preparation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Dried brewer's yeast powder (1320 g.) was treated with toluol (132 c.c.) and distilled water (1980 c.c.); the mixture was kept at 35° for 4 days. After this period of autolysis the mixture was diluted with distilled water (1800 c.c.) and filtered with kieselguhr under suction. The clear filtrate was put to a dialyser at 35°, fed with running tap water, and dialysis carried on for 48 hours using toluol to prevent putrefaction. The dialysed invertase extract (890 c.c.) was treated with an equal volume of absolute ethanol at pH 4.5, kept in

the cold (0-5°), and centrifuged. The precipitate was thereafter dissolved in 460 c.c. of water. Percentage of protein in this solution was 2.97. The original yeast powder (10 g.) was found to be equivalent to 11.4 c.c. of this invertase solution. The invertase activity was measured by the amount of reducing sugar formed by the enzyme which was determined by titration with Benedict's reagent. Titres corresponding to 10 g. yeast were calculated. The results are recorded in Tables I—III and in Fig 1.

The optimum percentage of inulin was found to be 20 g. in 200 c.c. of water to yield a comparable figure for the amount of reducing sugar liberated by the enzyme.

TABLE I

Substrate=sucrose (80 g.). Temp.=37.4°. Water=200 c.c. NaH₂PO₄ soln.=25 c.c.
Toluol=2 c.c.

Enzyme solution (2.97%).	Distilled water.	Invertase activity for 10 g. yeast powder (g.sugar)	Enzyme solution (2.97%).	Distilled water.	Invertase activity for 10g. yeast powder (g. sugar).
0.0 c.c.	20.0 c.c.	..	12.0 c.c.	8.0 c.c.	1.36 g.
2.0	18.0	5.17 g.	14.0	6.0	1.24
4.0	16.0	2.79	16.0	4.0	1.16
6.0	14.0	2.11	18.0	2.0	1.10
8.0	12.0	1.66	20.0	0.0	1.07
10.0	10.0	1.55			

N. B. pH remained at 4.8 sharp both before and after treatment.

TABLE II

Substrate=inulin (20 g.). Other conditions same as in Table I.

Enzyme soln. (2.97%)	Distilled water.	Invertase activity for 10 g. yeast powder (g.sugar).	Enzyme soln. (2.97%).	Distilled water.	Invertase activity for 10 g. yeast powder (g. sugar).
0.0 c.c.	20.0 c.c.	..	12.0. c.c.	8.0 c.c.	3.75 g.
2.0	18.0	17.90 g.	14.0	6.0	3.43
4.0	16.0	9.18	16.0	4.0	3.35
6.0	14.0	6.46	18.0	2.0	3.10
8.0	12.0	5.13	20.0	0.0	3.17
10.0	10.0	4.23			

N. B. pH remained at 5.0 exactly both before and after treatment.

TABLE III

Substrate=raffinose (20g.). Other conditions same as in Table I.

Enzyme soln. (2.97%).	Distilled water.	Invertase activity for 10 g. yeast (g. sugar)	Enzyme soln. (2.97%).	Distilled water.	Invertase activity for 10g. yeast (g. sugar).
0.0 c.c.	20.0 c.c.	..	12.0 c.c.	8.0 c.c.	1.16 g.
2.0	18.0	3.10 g.	14.0	6.0	1.24
4.0	16.0	1.74	16.0	4.0	1.21
6.0	14.0	1.36	18.0	2.0	1.25
8.0	12.0	1.24	20.0	0.0	1.29
10.0	10.0	1.16			

N. B. pH remained at 4.6 exactly both before and after treatment.

DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 (vide Tables I-III) represents the behaviour of purified invertase solution towards sucrose, raffinose, and inulin as substrates. The abscissae represent volumes of enzyme solution (2.97%) per 20 c.c. and the ordinates represent the enzyme activities for the substrates as measured by the amounts of reducing sugar liberated by the enzyme extract corresponding to 10 g. of brewer's yeast. Varying proportions of enzyme solution were used and activities corresponding to 10g. yeast powder calculated in each case. If there was no influence of the concentration of the enzyme on the substrate the activity curves should have been straight lines. But the graphs as drawn in the figure appear to be otherwise.

FIG. 1

The curve for inulin is much steeper than those for sucrose and raffinose. The curves for sucrose and raffinose are practically similar, the former being slightly steeper. The steepness of the curve for inulin suggests a higher rate of hydrolysis of the substrate at the initial concentrations of enzyme. Although inulin possesses considerable reducing power on Benedict's solution initially, the curves for sucrose and raffinose indicate a lower activity towards the enzyme. Thus there is some reasons to anticipate a decidedly distinct behaviour on the part of sucrose and raffinose as substrates, as compared with inulin. The work of Adams *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) has suggested the presence of a specific enzyme, inulase, in some of the enzyme preparations which behaves towards inulin in a specific way. Sreenivasya and Iyengar (*Nature*, 1933, 132, 604) effected a partial separation of invertase and inulase. The curve of inulin (Fig. 1) also suggests a specific behaviour of the invertase preparation from brewers' yeast towards inulin as compared with sucrose and raffinose, which practically belong to the same category.

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